

Advancements in Medical Imaging Technologies: Ultrasound, X-ray, and MRI

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Abstract:

Medical imaging is an important part of healthcare, aiding in the diagnosis, as well as the treatment and monitoring of diseases. The most common methods of modern medical diagnostics are ultrasound, X-ray and MRI. Ultrasound, X-ray and MRI are imaging technologies that have their advantages and disadvantages, as well as their fields of application. This article analyzes the advantages and disadvantages of each of the above technologies, as well as outlines the areas of application.

Keywords: *Medical imaging, healthcare technologies, diagnostics.*

Introduction to Medical Imaging

Medical imaging is a crucial part of healthcare, helping in diagnosis as well as treating and monitoring diseases. It is used to see the inside of the body, including the brain, tendons, muscles, blood vessels, and other organs, without the need for surgery or making a larger incision. In general, doctors usually start a diagnosis by using less harmful and less expensive imaging technologies, such as physical examination and the patient's medical history. However, medical imaging is often necessary to confirm the diagnosis, follow up on treatment, and monitor the progression of diseases and treatment.

Different types of medical imaging technologies are used for different parts of the body and conditions. Some of the common modern medical imaging technologies include computed tomography (CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and ultrasound imaging. In recent years, various advanced versions of conventional medical imaging technologies have been developed, capable of enhancing the performance and inferring complex physical characteristics of tissues, organs, and materials. The aim of this article is to provide fundamental knowledge and principles of some of the advanced modalities of medical imaging technologies. The next sections will provide fundamental knowledge and operational

principles of ultrasound, X-ray, and MRI technologies (Zhou, et al., 2021; Webb, 2022).

Importance of Diagnostic Imaging in Healthcare

One of the cornerstones of medicine is the capability to gain insights into the physiology of our bodies. No matter whether a patient has to be treated for a specific condition or to receive a clean bill of health, it is of utmost importance to be able to rely on imaging diagnosis. The technological advancements in medical imaging technologies offer a variety of benefits to the healthcare system, including enabling more accurate and quick diagnostics through the use of improved visualization, supporting greater skill to direct treatment more effectively, offering more in-depth, surgically relevant, and patient-specific insights with less risk, and providing an effective means for the treatment of interventional and surgical guidance.

The three techniques for medical imaging are ultrasound, x-ray, and MRI. While ultrasound method provides us with important information (such as local anatomical features) using soundwaves with abdominal and wrist sonography, it uses the Doppler effect to visualize blood flow in the heart, e.g. the echocardiography procedure. X-rays use ionizing radiation to provide two-dimensional images of the human body. Today, the most exceptional imaging technology is the MRI technique, which allows a variety of diagnostic applications by non-invasively displaying muscles, bones, major vessels, and the nervous and peripheral systems. Furthermore, MRI is free from ionizing radiation. This enables diagnostic examinations that require the use of x-rays, CT or angiography to be avoided, thereby reducing a significant source of radiation exposure for the population. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is extensively regarded as one of the most remarkable diagnostic advances in radiology since the development of x-rays because of these properties (Hussain, et al., 2022; Heiss, et al. 2021).

Ultrasound Technology

Medical imaging is a method to "see" what goes on inside the body. The process can be used to monitor diseases or act as a therapeutic tool. Ultrasound, X-ray, and magnetic resonance imaging are a few of the current medical imaging methods. An understanding of functioning medical imaging machinery is also central to understanding imaging methodologies. The portion of the sample that targets each application can be classified by various imaging methods. In recent decades, significant advances have been shown. Ergo, within this article, a compilation of recent advances in medical imaging technologies.

Ultrasound, often termed as sonography, is a method in which sound waves are used by medical practitioners to generate two or even three-dimensional photos within the body. In other words, this method passes sound pulses through the body and reflects off tissues they hit. The return waves are captured to generate a picture. This is the same way dolphins and other animals use echolocation to scan their surroundings. The usefulness of sound waves to generate pictures is based on two major factors. Sound waves have the advantage of penetrating the body within the range of 1-10 MHz, while others bounce off a highly dense or calcified surface. Therefore, sound waves could be used for investigations such as tracking pregnancies or tracking blood flow via the Doppler Effect. In addition to X-ray and MRI, sonography is another significant application in biomedical research. Ultrasound is less intrusive and less hazardous than similar photographs, presumably because sound waves are being used (Pinton, 2020; Lee, et al., 2020).

Principles of Ultrasound Imaging

Sound waves are waves of longitudinal or compressional motion of air molecules. Any sound wave has a frequency and a wavelength. Frequency is the number of sound waves that pass a fixed point in a certain amount of time. Wavelength, on the other hand, is the shortest distance between two points where the wave pattern repeats. The frequency and wavelength, as well as the speed of travel of the wave, are

related by the following equation: $\text{Speed} = \text{Frequency} \times \text{Wavelength}$ - that is why sound travels a shorter distance than light over the same time period. The audible range of frequencies is from 20 to 20,000 Hz. Frequencies greater than 20,000 Hz are known as ultrasonic or ultrasonic waves. Ultrasonic waves are also called ultrasound.

In a diagnostic ultrasound unit, a transducer is used in two ways: to produce the ultrasonic waves and then convert the returning waves into electrical signals. There are several factors that determine how successful this process could be: the wavelength of the wave, the frequency used, the mode in which the waves are traveling, that is, whether the wave is longitudinal, transverse, or surface waves, and the properties of the medium that carries the waves, sound is used in our body. When ultrasonic waves strike an interface between two media with different densities, such as soft tissue-bone, liquid-gas, or water-blood, a portion of the wave is reflected back to the surface of our body, and the rest is transmitted to continue the journey. At the receiving end of the unit, the returning waves are then converted into electric signals. The ultrasound image displays the distribution of the returning echoes as the various tissues absorb and reflect the ultrasonic waves to different degrees when struck (Chia, et al., 2023; Sehmbi, & Perlas, 2022).

Applications in Medical Diagnosis

In addition to its use for the study of structures, ultrasound is mainly used as a diagnostic tool. Ultrasound diagnosis is used on numerous occasions for different clinical circumstances and anatomic regions, primarily for its availability, affordability, wide spectrum of applications, and being easy to carry out. It is used extensively in general practice, acute hospital admissions, and in the patients' homes by a wide variety of health professionals.

1. Prenatal Evaluation

The most common indication for fetal ultrasonography is dating (gestational age, menstrual dating, pregnancy, IVF in vitro fertilization), confirmation of viability (e.g.

retained products of conception, incomplete miscarriage), suspected Rhesus iso-immunization, anomaly scan, amniotic fluid assessment (oligohydramnios, polyhydramnios), estimated fetal weight, fetal position, and presentation. Common prenatal ultrasound screening indications are identification of placenta previa, multiple pregnancies, sex selection, chorionic villous sampling, amniocentesis, antenatal fetal surveillance during high-risk pregnancy e.g. diabetes, hypertension. Ultrasound when used for prenatal diagnosis has many benefits, including providing high sensitivity and specificity for intrauterine fetal malformations, no ionizing radiation, ability to scan in any plane, ability to differentiate fluid from solid masses, ability to hear fetal heart and movements, ability to do Doppler studies to measure blood, and allowing parents to see the fetus.

2. Some Urological Applications

Ultrasound is the gold standard investigation of the kidneys. Urinary tract conditions commonly assessed with ultrasound are kidney stones, pyelonephritis, renal cysts, and renal carcinoma. In some circumstances, ultrasound is the only form of imaging the urinary tracts available to the clinicians. The first 10th most common general practice presentation; one indication for urinary tract scanning is hematuria. The nature of the creation of the images can affect the resolution within the kidneys. Carcinoma detection/characterization properties i.e. treatment planning. Musculoskeletal applications e.g. soft tissue abscess or osteomyelitis (Singla, et al., 2022).

X-ray Imaging

In 1895, just weeks after the discovery of fireworks, an unseen discovery was presented by Wilhelm Röntgen, a German professor of physics. He discovered X-rays and found that they could penetrate most solid objects, including the human body, allowing the bones inside to be photographed. Although the fundamentals of X-rays for medical imaging have remained unchanged for well over a

century, there have been several advancements. Improved radiation detection and readout technologies have improved the equipment used to develop X-ray images. Modern digital X-rays are captured via an electronic charge-coupled device (CCD), where the imaging plate is replaced by a digital sensor.

To what extent is an X-ray relevant to modern medical imaging? It can be used to image any dense, solid object, but it is particularly useful when it comes to imaging bones and dental cavities. During a typical X-ray, the patient's body absorbs some of the X-rays, and the rest pass through to an X-ray detector. When the X-rays hit the detector, they either pass right through or are partially absorbed. The result is an X-ray image, or radiography. X-rays are useful in detecting clear absences, but they are not so useful when something is only partially present or weakly present. For example, it is difficult to identify differences in muscle structures via X-ray.

However, in the field of chest medicine, X-ray is widely used to see the structure of the lungs. X-ray provides the best image for analyzing and diagnosing structural diseases, such as pneumonia, bronchitis, tuberculosis, and lung cancer. Similarly, in the field of cardiology, X-ray is used to check the anatomy of the blood chambers, locate the artificial valves, and see the main vessels. In trauma, X-ray is again efficient to see bone fractures rather than muscular swelling. The technology is considered the "gold standard" for seeing bone swellings or fractures in many cases (Bhandary, et al., 2020; Çalli, Sogancioglu, & van Ginneken, 2021).

Fundamentals of X-ray Technology

X-ray technology is a great achievement of science and an indispensable tool in diagnostics. It allows visualizing the interior structures of biological objects - from the simplest forms of life to humans. Visual clarity, radiation dose to the test subject, and cost are in the core of each respective clinician. Thus, X-ray technology with its moderately low budget and widely scalable spatial resolution provides essential help in medicine. X-rays are good at visualizing dense tissues inside the body, thus providing invaluable

information in case of bone fractures and hernias, a wide range of infections, also examining chest diseases like pneumonia, pleurisy associated with lung base collapse (atelectasis), fluid in the chest (pleural effusion), and any identification of anatomical additions.

X-rays are part of the electromagnetic spectrum, just like rays, microwaves, and visible light. The medical X-ray has energy values ranging from 5 to 150 keV; based on this, their wavelength comes between 0.002 and 0.01 nm. In the X-ray tube, X-rays are produced by bombarding a heavy-metal anode with high-energy electrons traveling with a speed of 50 keV to 125 keV. This knocking out of K-shell electrons is followed by the filling of the vacancy by the transition of L-shell electrons to K-shell. Thus, $K\alpha$ rays are produced. Additionally, the L-shell electrons also fill the vacancy created by the transition of K-shell to L-shell, resulting in $L\alpha$ and $L\beta$ X-rays. The outputs - X-rays - are produced when highly energetic electrons from the cathode collide with a target material, usually a heavy element such as tungsten (Poirier, et al., 2020; Omar, Andreo, & Poludniowski, 2020).

Clinical Applications and Limitations

X-ray can reveal bones and soft tissue that contain a different mineral content, providing different contrast absorption coefficients. X-ray diagnostic imaging today is widely used in clinical settings. It can reveal the internal structure of the human body, diagnosing a full range of diseases from cavities, fractures, to pneumonia as it cannot go through water and fat, and bone, shown with the contrast. Furthermore, iodine as a foreign contrast agent can reveal blood vessels. X-ray is widely used in diagnosis and treatment (from orthopedic surgeries to cardiologic operations).

The application of different imaging modalities depends on healthcare conditions, the expertise of medical professionals, and the general preference of the patient. Furthermore, an optimal decision-making process requires a full understanding of their physical principles and limitations. There are obvious contraindications in unhealthy applications of radiation. Therefore, radiation protection in X-ray

examination is a significant focus. The goal of radiation protection is to secure the patients from irrational exposure to radiation. Strict rules have been established to avoid the use of radiation in pregnant women and children, unless the diagnosis is critical. In addition, poorly exposed X-ray sensors may not provide sharp images as obese individuals have greater density in tissue. In reality, studies show that metallic implants such as joint prostheses, cardiac valves, and dental crowns produce imperfections such as scattering, streaking, and shading in X-ray imaging. Moreover, X-ray makes it technically challenging and impractical to acquire a fine soft tissue contrast with this modality. In such cases, ultrasound and MRI will provide a better outcome. Although X-ray imaging is providing many beneficial images and applications in clinical, it has obvious limitations and considerations (Tsapaki, 2020; Jeukens, et al., 2020).

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is an imaging technique that is used to determine the anatomy and structural integrity without the need for ionizing radiation. This is because it is based on the magnetic properties of atomic nuclei, especially hydrogen atoms. Each hydrogen nucleus is a magnet that rotates on its own axis at an angle of 90 degrees to the external magnetic field. When a radio frequency pulse is sent, it causes the hydrogen protons to vibrate at a different angle. When the magnetic field stops, these protons reverse to their original position, causing a radio signal to be sent.

A computer processes the signals and presents them in a two- or three-dimensional form. The intensity and distribution of the signals may vary from one tissue to another since the parameters associated with the signals are proportional to the signal-to-noise ratio, the repetition time, and the time of the reflex proposal. There are specific clinical conditions in which MRI may be considered the best imaging modality. Physiological processes can be detected by MR imaging, such as blood flow. The method of fat

suppression also enables better visualization of focal lesions.

Disadvantages of MRI include the fact that the quality of the MR image is considerably influenced by slight patient movement and metallic and other objects. As the MR images are taken while the patient is breathing, they may have blurred structures, which sometimes makes them difficult to interpret. The method involves lying a motionless patient in a confining noisy tube, which may not be suitable for claustrophobic patients. Some metallic objects scatter the image qualities, producing artifacts. Headaches may be caused due to the noise of the scanner. In the absence of any undue risks associated with metallic implants, the technique is exceptionally safe. The use of Gadolinium chelates, in particular, may induce rare cases of nephrogenic systemic fibrosis. Studies up to now have not shown MRI to have adverse effects on pregnant women and their babies (Peschke, et al., 2021; Van Speybroeck, O'Reilly, & Teeuwisse, 2021).

Basic Principles of MRI

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a medical imaging technique used to visualize internal structures of the human body. This imaging method employs a strong magnetic field to polarize nuclei in the body in order to detect faint signals emitted by the nuclei in response to radiofrequency energy. The magnetic field generated by MRI systems is produced by superconducting magnets or less powerful permanent magnets, which are powerful enough to affect and temporarily realign the magnetic field of the nuclei in the body. When these superconducting magnets generate the magnetic field, the body is positioned such that the magnetic field acts in the longitudinal direction with the body axis and is in the same direction as the MRI machine cylinder bore (either 1.5 tesla or 3 tesla). A primarily strong static magnetic field lines up the nuclei of hydrogen atoms, in particular, those of the protons in the tissue, and the magnetic field polarizes these protons by aligning the axes of protons.

In the second step, protons absorb a radiofrequency (RF) pulse with the proper

frequency applied perpendicular to the static magnetic field, which causes the protons to flip from the longitudinal axis to the transverse axis. And then, the energy in the RF pulse is discontinued, and the protons return to their natural state. As they do so, they emit RF signals that, once measured and analyzed, provide clear, detailed pictures of the internal body structures in three planes (x, y, and z planes). Then, the RF signal emits energy to the human body, which is detected as the radio receiver. The local gradient magnetic fields make the additional field with the permanent magnetic field. This makes the local magnetic field variation after the radiofrequency pulse, which is the key to the spatial information of the image (Paganetti, et al., 2021; Pfützner, Mukha, & Wang, 2023).

Advantages and Disadvantages

The MRI may encounter some difficulties during the clinical applications; however, it is still considered to be one of the greatest imaging modality techniques because of its being a non-invasive, multi-planar examination with excellent soft tissue contrast. Furthermore, functional MRI (fMRI) can depict the part of the human brain responsible for motor, visual, auditory, and sensory personalities which enable the researchers to discover the effect of drug, medicine, alcohol, stroke, and other brain diseases.

Another main advantage of MRI is the absence of ionizing radiation that can be a unique factor in the routine practice involving children and pregnant women. Contrast medium is used in MRI to improve the highlighting of various tissues or blood vessels. A contrast medium is made up of gadolinium, and it is less dangerous than other materials containing iodine. The MRI examination could be enhanced by using a contrast medium in various applications, whether in brain, head and neck, bony cysts, blood vessels, organs, muscles, joints, or general lesions. Disadvantages include a long acquisition time, a relatively high price, patient compliance (young children, severely claustrophobic, and psychologically impaired), an inability to scan because of the presence of metallic foreign bodies, such as ferromagnetic, and a limited

availability in some areas. Some patients cannot move at all since a drug that makes them sleep and relax might influence the diagnosis process. The fMRI also has a certain side effect that can hypnotize the brain. In some cases, nausea, skin rash, itching, or swelling sometimes results in contrast-enhanced MRI.

Conclusion

In summary, the availability of diverse medical imaging technologies presents a greater potential to analyze and understand health issues. Moreover, with ongoing improvements in technology, the contrast resolution and detection capability of these techniques are consistently improving. This has, in turn, established a fast-growing interest in adopting these advancements for better healthcare services.

The ultrasound, X-ray, and MRI all involve imaging technologies that have specific strengths and limitations. In its true function, the ultrasound is used for morphological diagnosis. Although ultrasound is not particularly optimal as the X-ray, the ultrasound can be used to evaluate further abnormalities but does not require a well-structured anatomical analysis. The X-ray is the perfect tool for individuals in the morphological part, smaller with a larger number of details that are required. However, the larger the KoV, the greater the radiation dose that must be received by the staff, patient, and diagnosis. In many cases, the differences between ultrasound and X-ray appliances in terms of diagnosis are very clear. The strength of MRI lies in the ability to generate large images with quality from soft tissues without exposing the human body to ionizing radiation, or any radiation that must be experienced using CT scans and X-rays. The weakness includes the fact that for patients with pacemakers, MRI is not recommended, as well as those who have claustrophobia because the tunnel-shaped MRI examination room and the lure that patients must use is a problem for some people. Talking about whether it recently dominates the modality used in medical diagnosis? The MRI modality scanner uses 1.5T most commonly, followed by

the 3.0T, and for high-field strength 7.0T/9.4T MRI modality is used for special studies.

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